

**IDEOLOGICAL POLARIZATION AND AFFECTIVE POLARIZATION AMONG
SELECTED REGISTERED VOTERS IN BARANGAY SAN FRANCISCO
GENERAL TRIAS CITY, CAVITE**

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the level of ideological polarization among selected registered voters in terms of political concepts, social issues, and economic issues; determine the level of affective polarization among selected registered voters in terms of in-group feelings and out-group feelings; and identify the relationship between the level of ideological polarization and level of affective polarization among selected registered voters. The researchers utilized a quantitative method with correlational design in the study to effectively identify the relationship of the variables. It took place on Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite from where the 380 registered voters were surveyed. Survey questionnaire was utilized by the researchers in gathering the data. The results revealed that the respondents have moderate level of ideological polarization ($Mdn = 2.81$) which implies that their ideological beliefs are not solely limited between two rivaling ideologies. Likewise, the respondents have moderate level of affective polarization ($M = 2.60$, $SD = 0.60$) which only implies that they have ordinary level of hostility and affability towards their in-group and out-group. Lastly, Kendall's tau-B correlation revealed that the two variables have a significant weak positive correlation.

Keywords: *registered voters, political landscape, political beliefs, ideological orientations*

INTRODUCTION

Concomitant with a democratic political regime is the electorates' guaranteed exercise of speech freedom and voting right which both as key mechanism of democracy, in their natural manner, agrees the establishment of a plural and tolerant society from there shall be a harmless and healthy co-existence of multiple political views. However, this does not seem applicable and true in recent years as annoyance and aversion have become the natural feelings of individuals toward another group of individuals who have different political outlooks. Today, political differences are treated cynically making it inseparable from negative feelings which in turn had resulted to cancel culture, hate speeches, relationship loss, and worst political polarization.

Unfortunately, it is highly evident in the recent political landscape of the Philippines as the conclusion of the 2022 national election had left a starkly divided Filipinos based on each presidential bet. Indeed, that is when hurtful exchange of lines, blocking, and unfriending began dominating social media platforms, and that primarily concerns mass affective polarization.

Polarization in the simplest fashion is a division into two sharply opposing groups. Ferraris (2023) specified two elements that must coincide for a society to be considered polarized, these are high within-cluster similarity and high between-cluster dissimilarity. Ideological polarization happens when beliefs, opinions, and values become bimodally positioned at both extremes (Jost et al., 2021). Affective Polarization is the level to which people feel empathy towards their in-groups and antagonism towards their out-groups. The said types are mutually reinforcing and some of the previous studies have proven their relationships. Polarization might cause democratic recession which primarily involves deterioration of democratic institutions and infringement of individual rights. Moreover, polarization on people will trigger intolerance, avoidance, discrimination, political violence, and worst civil war.

The existing studies on this matter were focused primarily on the United States and other European countries and little to zero has been done in the Philippines so the results of those cannot be justified and extended in the country. The study could be the starting point for further interest in the subject to gradually see the potential of the phenomenon in the entire country.

The present study will ascertain the substantial correlation among ideological and affective polarization. Specifically, between the electorate's expressed and observed negative feeling towards out-group and positive feeling towards in-group and their differences on ideological beliefs.

Since the study is about finding relations, the researchers utilized a quantitative method with correlational design to effectively describe the relationship of the variables. The researchers chose Barangay San Francisco, General Trias Cavite as the locale of the study where it surveyed 380 electorates after the employment of purposive sampling.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

The figure presented below is the researchers portrayed framework of the study:

Figure 1. Research paradigm

This conceptual framework was put together as a model to illustrate how the variables were treated in the study. Since this is a correlational study, cause and effect was not established and there is no distinction between the dependent and independent variables. These are predicted to change in response to each other. Therefore, the paradigm indicates that ideological polarization affects the development of affective polarization and vice versa. This is called a two directional relationship. Double headed arrow was used to represent the association or the covariance of the two.

Research Questions

This study determined the relationship between ideological polarization and affective polarization among selected registered voters in Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite. Specifically, it provided answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of ideological polarization among selected registered voters in Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite in terms of:
 - a. political concepts;
 - b. social issues; and
 - c. economic issues?
2. What is the level of affective polarization among selected registered voters in Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite in terms of:
 - a. in-group feelings; and
 - b. out-group feelings?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of ideological polarization and affective polarization among selected registered voters in Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, participants of the study, sampling method, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations.

Since the main concern of the study is the relationship between ideological polarization and affective polarization, the researchers employed a quantitative method with correlational research design to effectively determine the relationship of the involved variables. Specifically, a structured questionnaire with Likert scale type of questions was utilized in conducting this study.

According to Mbuva (2023), research with quantitative correlation design is a field of non-experimentation that includes the calculation of variables numerically, examining if they are related, identifying the direction of any correlations, and determining the degree of correlations. Among quantitative research, survey method was used by the researchers to accurately measure the variables.

The target population of the study were the registered voters of Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite which was minimized from 33450 registered voters to only 380 respondents after the employment Raosoft online calculator. The said figure was taken out of the 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level.

The researchers utilized purposive sampling in choosing units for analysis. The identified 380 respondents from the calculation were registered voters of Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite. Likewise, the said respondents have collectively experienced being annoyed to someone who share different political beliefs and believes that the Filipino public today are divided in their political beliefs.

Data were collected through the survey to the respondents. Specifically, it employed a self-made questionnaire containing questions based on the statement of the problem. The type of questions were Likert scale survey questions.

The researchers, through the letter of request signed by the thesis adviser asked permission to conduct the study in Barangay San Francisco, City of General Trias, Cavite. The researchers visited certain subdivisions in the locale that enabled them to easily fill the required number of participants. They sought the guidance of Barangay personnel on which subdivisions to visit since the researchers were not from the place.

The survey questionnaire was divided into two parts. The first part is composed of statements about ideological beliefs from which the respondents gauged their agreement that eventually determined the ideological polarization. The second part is composed of statements about potential feelings a person has towards their in-group and out-group from which the respondents gauged their level of agreement that eventually determined the affective polarization. For both parts, a 4-point agreement Likert scale was utilized. Ten to Fifteen minutes is the projected time duration of answering the survey questionnaire. Questions about ideological polarization are primarily constructed using the book entitled "Political Ideologies, An Introduction" 6th Edition of Andrew Heywood that was published in 2017, while questions about affective polarization are formulated based on the generally observed feelings of people joint with the results of some previous related studies. The researchers made sure that the questions were written in both English and Filipino language with the use of layman's term. The survey questionnaire

was validated by three experts and undergone pre-testing. Following the survey, the data collected from the respondents were analysed and quantified.

Given the study is a quantitative approach, the collected data by the researchers were treated fairly and correctly using statistics. The organization, analyzation, and interpretation were entirely based on numbers. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in the treatment of data. After collection, results were tallied first then accurate statistical treatment depending on each objective were applied. Afterwards, interpretation was done. Lastly, graphs and tables with short explanation were provided to best present the findings. Composite mean, median, standard deviation and median absolute deviation (MAD) were utilized to determine both the level of ideological and affective polarization. To identify the relationship between the level ideological polarization and affective polarization, Kendall's tau-B correlation was employed. The Kendall's tau-B correlation was used to determine if there was a positive or negative relationship between the two variables or no relationship at all.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the interpretation of the data and results generated from the 380 selected registered voters of Barangay San Francisco, General Trias City, Cavite. The findings of the study are discussed herein according to the presentation and order of the statement of the problem.

Table 1 shows the level of ideological polarization among the selected registered voters of Brgy. San Francisco, City of General Trias, Cavite ($n = 380$). Overall, the respondents have moderate level of ideological polarization ($Mdn = 2.81$). This indicates that the registered voters possess approximately parallel ideological beliefs from each other which is either they have shared neutral or middle beliefs or a shared mixed of ideological beliefs across various topic and issues. Similarly, this implies that their ideological beliefs are not constrained solely between two competing ideologies on the political spectrum.

Table 1. Level of ideological polarization among the respondents ($n = 380$)

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>Political Concepts</i>			
1. I believe that freedom is a God-given natural right and not a privilege given by the government.	3.45	0.80	High
2. I believe that authority is unquestionable	2.33	1.08	Low

3. I believe that authority is meant to be exercised by gifted individuals only.	2.32	1.11	Low
4. I believe that the leader's power to govern is absolute.	2.17	1.05	Low
5. I believe that humans cannot reach perfection as they are born to be intellectually limited.	2.84	1.02	Moderate
6. I believe that culture makes people unite and allows them to work together.	3.29	0.81	Moderate
7. I believe that gender shows what men and women can do in the society.	2.42	1.08	Low
8. I believe that the state and government only work for the benefit of the rich people.	2.52	1.06	Low
<hr/> <i>Social Issues</i> <hr/>			
1. I believe that homosexuality must be accepted by society.	3.01	0.93	Moderate
2. I believe that same- sex marriage must be enacted.	2.65	0.96	Moderate
3. I believe that abortion is a personal choice of woman.	2.49	1.15	Low
4. I believe that abortion must be legalized in our country)	1.87	0.97	Low
5. I believe that laws are only followed by people because they are afraid of punishment.	2.75	0.96	Moderate
6. I believe that citizens should have the approval of the laws and policies in the country.	3.11	0.93	Moderate
7. I believe that government should focus on making our military defense strong to protect our national interest.	3.22	0.94	Moderate

8. I believe that globalization causes the country to lose its national identity.	2.77	1.04	Moderate
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Economic Issues

1. I believe that rich people and big businesses shall be collected higher tax.	3.28	0.97	Moderate
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2. I believe that the government should intervene and regulate businesses in the country.	3.07	0.92	Moderate
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3. I believe that the tax of citizens should return to them through social welfare programs of the government.	3.54	0.81	High
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4. I believe that having personal property encourages people to become materialistic and selfish.	2.44	1.02	Low
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5. I believe that people are poor because they are lazy.	2.63	1.21	Moderate
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6. I believe that people are poor because of the lack of job opportunities.	3.02	1.00	Moderate
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7. I believe that through hard work and determination people can rise from poverty.	3.23	1.10	Moderate
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8. I believe that territorial conquest is an acceptable way to increase the country's resources.	1.92	1.00	Low
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9. I believe that Filipino-made products are the best in the world.	3.17	0.87	Moderate
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10. I believe that, we, Filipinos must buy and patronize our own products.	3.46	0.78	High
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Median		2.81	
Median Absolute Deviation		0.25	
Verbal Interpretation			Moderate Ideological Polarization

Note. 1.00-1.79 – Very Low Ideological Polarization
 1.80-2.59 – Low Ideological Polarization
 2.60-3.39 – Moderate Ideological Polarization
 3.40-4.19 – High Ideological Polarization
 4.20-5.00 – Very High Ideological Polarization

Table 2 shows the level of affective polarization among the selected registered voters of Brgy. San Francisco, City of General Trias, Cavite (n = 380). Overall, the respondents have moderate level of affective polarization (M = 2.60, SD = 0.60). This indicates that people’s views based on feelings and emotion were relatively divided. It means that the registered voters favor their in-group not too high nor too low, just the same as they do not get too aggressive or hostile towards the people they don’t belong with. This somewhat affirmed the study of Rieljan (2021) wherein he said that the Netherlands, Southeast Asia and the Nordic Countries were the least affectively polarized places. Philippines is part of Southeast Asia, and this study revealed that people are moderately affective.

Table 2. Level of affective polarization among the respondents (n = 380)

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
<i>In-Group Feelings</i>			
1.I wanted to be with or near to people who share my/our politic	3.08	0.81	Moderate
2. I am happy and contented with my/our own political beliefs.	3.04	0.81	Moderate
3. I am not interested on other political beliefs.	2.50	0.91	Low
4.I feel confident in the accuracy of my/our own political beliefs and ready to defend it wherever I go.	3.07	0.77	Moderate
5. I am always excited to meet people that will support more my political beliefs	3.24	0.77	Moderate
6. I feel proud of myself when I get other people to believe and agree on my/our political beliefs	3.18	0.83	Moderate
7. I admire people for shifting away from their previous political beliefs to my political beliefs.	3.01	0.87	Moderate

8. I feel appreciated when other people try to listen and understand my/our political beliefs.	3.31	0.76	Moderate
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Out-Group Feelings

1. I don't want to be friends with people who do not share my/our political beliefs.	2.26	0.99	Low
2. I don't want to be with people who do not share my/our political beliefs.	2.32	1.00	Low
3. I am willing to cut off any relations to people who has different political beliefs.	2.19	1.01	Low
4. I avoid my friends/relatives acquaintances/workmates when their political beliefs are different from me.	2.17	1.00	Low
5. I block and unfriend on Facebook my friends/relatives/ acquaintances/workmates when their political beliefs are different from me.	2.05	1.00	Low
6. I am annoyed when someone talks about his/her different political beliefs	2.26	1.03	Low
7. I feel satisfied/good when people are embarrassed because of their different political belief	2.07	1.06	Low
8. I feel hurt, jealous and envious when other people are convinced by other political beliefs	2.12	1.01	Low
9. I feel mad when followers of other political beliefs laugh or make fun of my/our political beliefs.	2.45	1.03	Low

10. I feel insulted by people who do not listen and understand my political beliefs.	2.44	0.99	Low
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Mean	2.60
Standard Deviation	0.60
Verbal Interpretation	Moderate Affective Polarization

Note. 1.00-1.79 – Very Low Ideological Polarization
1.80-2.59 – Low Ideological Polarization
2.60-3.39 – Moderate Ideological Polarization
3.40-4.19 – High Ideological Polarization
4.20-5.00 – Very High Ideological Polarization

As shown in the table for the in-group feelings, almost all the statements got the interpretation of moderate level of affective polarization except statement number 3. It implies that people have an average optimistic view on their own beliefs as well as average positive feeling for the people belonging in their group. It is supported by the study of Turner-Zwinkels et al (2023) where individuals tend to favor their own group compared to others. Moreover, Statement 8 “I feel appreciated when other people try to listen and understand my/our own political beliefs” obtained the highest mean followed by the statement 5 “I am always excited to meet people that will support more my political beliefs” and statement 6 “I feel proud of myself when I get other people to believe and agree on my political beliefs” with verbal interpretation of moderate affective polarization. It signifies that is easier for a person to socialize, have connections with and get to know others who share the same beliefs and sentiments as them. Yet it could also be drawn here that it is not necessary to convert or believe to a person’s notion, what matters is that the energy is reciprocated, and a person is trying and willing to listen to another. Related to this is the study of Solomon et al. (2018), wherein politicians who belonged to the same political party was perceived to have higher rating of character than those in outgroup.

Additionally, it is also noteworthy that registered voters are reasonably happy to be with like-minded people. Statement 1 “I wanted to be with or near to people who share my/our political beliefs” resulted too moderately divided. It means that in most circumstances, they are comfortable and feel safe to converse and discuss to the people who have the same political principles and values as them. It was supported by study of Gimpel &Hui (2015), people seek neighbourhood that is politically compatible to them favouring those with the same partisan composition as them.

The statement which got lowest mean is statement 3 “I am not interested on other political beliefs. It has verbal interpretation of low affective polarization. It implies its contrary which means that people appeared to be open minded and are interested in starting conversation with other people who have different political impressions. They are willing to entertain, evaluate and scrutinize one’s beliefs that are discrete from them showing that they are understanding. It rejects the findings of Han & Shim (2018) where people refuse to participate in substantial negotiations and are unwilling to accept any compromises due to the intense emotional confrontation.

For the outgroup feelings, all statements fall on the verbal interpretation of low affective polarization which indicates that while people have average positive outlook on the group they belong with, they were not that hostile nor angry to the opposite political belief's believers. There is a division, but it is in the low level only which means that they do not close doors to the opposing adherent of other political belief and still has a way to minimize.

On top of that, the statement which attain the highest mean is statement 9 "I feel mad when followers of other political beliefs laugh or make fun of my/our own political beliefs" then statement 10 "I feel insulted by people who do not listen and understand my political beliefs". These fall on the low affective polarization which means that there is a stubby feeling of indifference, but they are not mad towards outgroups. It indicates that they are just a little bit annoyed at being laughed about based on their political preferences, making them slightly irritated whenever they are not heard, understood, and listened to or when they can't defend their own political stance. It contrasted the result of the study in America by Iyengar et al (2019) wherein it shows that there is a growing dislike and distrust from people of other party asserting that its members are hypocritical, selfish and closeminded and are unwilling to socialize across party lines.

Notable also in these is the statement 1 which says that registered voters didn't want to be friend with people who do not share the same political beliefs. It implies that similarity in political preferences is someway one of the criteria in finding friends and having differences gives to some extent a negative outlook on a person. It somewhat affirmed the result of the survey data from the Pew Research Centre wherein approximately 64% of Democrats and 55% of Republicans report having "just a few" or "no" close friends who belong to the opposing political party.

The lowest mean obtained for the outgroup feelings is the statement 5 "I block and unfriend on Facebook my friends'/relatives'/ acquaintances/workmates when their political beliefs are different from me" with interpretation of low affective polarization. It suggests that Filipinos despite being different in political adherents stills value the relationship to others and does not resort to immediate blocking or unfriending them specifically to Facebook. It affirmed the study of Bode (2016), wherein the result of the survey data of Pew Research Centre reveals that engaging in activities such as unfriending is relatively rare, with fewer than 10% of respondents practicing. It denotes that political disagreement is not the key player in blocking or unfriending others. Again, with the combined result of ingroup and outgroup feelings, the registered voters are moderately affective polarized.

Table 3 shows the result of the analysis of the relationship between the ideological and affective polarization among the respondents (n = 380). Kendall's tau-B correlation revealed that the two variables have a significant weak positive correlation, $\tau_b = 0.37$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.31, 0.43] with a weak effect size. This suggests that as the ideologies of the registered voters become more divided, the higher the chance and intensity that they will be hostile among voters who have opposing political beliefs while expressing

affiliation and admiration towards those whom they share their ideologies with, and vice-versa.

Table 3. Kendall's tau-B correlation for the relationship between the ideological and affective polarization among the respondents ($n = 380$)

Paired Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Ideological and Affective Polarization	0.37***	<.001	Reject the null hypothesis	Weak Positive Correlation

Note. If $p < .05$, reject the null hypothesis.
 If $p > .05$, fail to reject the null hypothesis.
 ***Significant at .001 level.

Moreover, this result indicates that the as the similarities of ideologies among the registered voters grow as well as the dissimilarity from other adherent of opposing ideologies, the animosity and affability also grows, the former is to those who don't share their ideologies and the latter for those who share it. Likewise, the correlation implies that similarity attracts, and difference repels. As voters become consistent with his ideological beliefs and inconsistent with the opposing side ideology, they will also exhibit feeling of favouritism on their own and aversion on the other.

This type of relationship was supported by the study of Reiljan (2021), ideologically more divided persons and countries are also more intense concerning affective feelings towards factions. However, it was also established in the study that even though these 2 may overlap, it may only do in restricted extent as they are two distinct concepts. In contrary, it was argued that ideological divide is not a necessary condition for affective polarization. Accordingly, in few circumstances, affective polarization can grow while ideological divisions shrink (Iyengar et al, 2019).

DISCUSSION

Searching about polarization would not disappoint a researcher for a corsage of publications that can be discovered and scrutinized. Certainly, political polarization in today's time has accumulated the interest of scholars and academicians across the world due to its proven increasing persistence and as a result, been the subject of studies and articles from different fields.

Advancing is how political polarization described in the United States and it is said to extend all over the world (Kubin & Sikorski, 2021). It was also supported by Carothers and O'Donuhue (2019) wherein they initially stated in their analysis that polarization in the world is oscillating democratic societies from the old to just newly established ones. Contrastingly, if the benchmark of comparison is on the ability to spawn a civil war, today would certainly become nought as those in the preceding times were leading up to civilian warfare but rarely to be sustained for a long time. It was also noted that what we have in

the present day is remarkably akin to the politics of the Post-Reconstruction Era. (Pierson & Schickler, 2020)

In the paper “How Party Polarization Affects Governance” Lee (2015) defines polarization in the simplest sense as the two opposing factions being extremely separated. A similar perspective was also expressed by Jost et al., (2022) as they saw its possibility to be employed in depicting the conditions of intergroup relationships identifying it as an enormous or widening gap between two or more factions

Incongruent with the two prior layman’s conceptions, Schedler (2023) provided a technical and wider picture of polarization by using a conflict analytic approach in the article “Rethinking Political Polarization”. Under the perspective of the macro-structure of conflict, it was declared that the entire countries, polities, or regimes are what denoted in political polarization, having the highest level of collective conflict that creates a division line on the entire nation. Among the other specified four, the third and fourth are the most relevant. On the third implication, bipolar conflicts among two dominant camps are what being referred which eliminates the existence of multipolar competition. Consistent with this are the elements stated in Lee (2015), to be considered polarized, the preferences of members shall become more distinctly bimodal and that the two modes are moving farther apart. For Ferraris (2023), there must be a presence of both “high within-cluster similarity” and “high between-cluster dissimilarity”. On the final level of the macro-structure of conflict, which is said to be the extreme level, that is when polarization forms a partitioning line between political actors that reposition, subservient, or replace all other forms of political division.

Backing the result of this paper, in Table 1, it was supported in the study of Jou (2010) stating the low figure of the Philippines about left-right polarization when compared to other countries being studied. It got a score of 3.93, the lowest among the examined countries. In the study of Layu (2020), moderate ideological orientations were affirmed to indicate a quite low degree of division due to the distribution of the ideological alignments characterized as unimodal and centrist. Social media has become a crucial part of politics, providing platforms that enable individuals to seek political information, share political opinions, and engage in online discussions.

The result is also comparable to the study of Akaliyski (2023) in East Asia wherein it was asserted that East Asian societies exhibit a specific pattern of support of freedom with extensive stress on strong personal autonomy. On the other hand, statements 2, 3, and 4 got the lowest mean. The said items are conservative ideological statements from which most of the respondents disagreed that equate the fact that they do not hold conservative belief on the concept of authority nor specify their ideological belief on the topic. It is also presumed therein that their ideological orientation on the topic was from other ideologies. It is statement number 4: “I believe that authority is unquestionable” which got the lowest mean equating the low agreement of the respondents also. The statement is a manifestation of an autocratic system of government which is also unpopular and rejected by half or more of Canadians and Europeans revealing that is a very bad way to govern (Wike et al., 2024). Furthermore, the ideological polarization on

concept of gender, and the state and government are low implying their ideological beliefs to be dispersed along the ideological continuum.

Moreover, for political concepts, it is statements number 1, 5, and 6 which greatly shows a collective and substantial level of ideological polarization. This suggests that while the registered voters have high agreement of the liberal conception of freedom, it also opposes their idea about human and culture which are falling from the conservative ideology. Among the indicators under political concepts, it is statement number 1 “I believe that freedom is a God-given natural right and not a privilege given by the government.” which got the highest mean with the verbal interpretation of high ideological polarization. This only signifies that most of the registered voters have liberal view of freedom suggesting a high within cluster similarity. This result is comparable to the study in East Asia wherein it was asserted that East Asian Societies exhibits a specific pattern of support of freedom with extensive stress on strong personal autonomy. On the other hand, it is statements 2, 3, and 4 which got the lowest mean. The said items are conservative ideological statements from which most of the respondents disagreed that equate the fact that they do not hold conservative belief on the concept of authority nor specify their ideological belief on the topic. It is also presumed therein that their ideological orientation on the topic was from other ideologies. Furthermore, the ideological polarization on concept of gender, and the state and government are low implying their ideological beliefs to be dispersed along the ideological continuum.

Under social issues, even though most of the indicators show moderate level of ideological polarization except statement 3 and 4, it is remarkable how they also contradict one another. For instance, item number 1 and seven 7 both expresses different ideological principles yet obtained the same level of agreement which truly demonstrates the moderate division of registered voters on their ideological beliefs. Among the indicators under social issues, it is statement number 7 which got the highest mean, it underlies an ideology from the right due to its character of militarism, struggle, and tendency to war which truly oppose statement number 6, 1, and 2 due to its collective character from the left. In addition, it is statement 3 and 4 which got the lowest agreement and mean among social issues with both interpretation of low ideological polarization, it signifies that while they are being pessimistic about their stand about abortion it is also presumed to be falling on other ideologies hence, it may be mixed or dispersed. This result supports the report of Pew Research Center which says that there is a balance of opinion or middle ground approach among Americans. Correspondingly, indicator number 1 and 2, ideological statements about homosexuality and same-sex marriage reveal a moderate level of ideological polarization which implies that they are not certain to what position they hold whether it shall be allowed or not in which the common circumstance is they believe that homosexuality must be allowed but not the same- sex marriage.

Regarding economic issues, it is obvious how the level of ideological polarization stretches from different levels from low to high. As shown in table, it is statement number 3 “I believe that the tax of citizens should return to them through social welfare programs of the government” which got the highest mean among economic issues with a verbal interpretation of high ideological polarization. The issue being featured in the statement

are tax and social welfare programs which falls to an ideology from left and indicates that the government should do more to better the life of the people. The said statement has a high ideological polarization interpretation due to high within cluster similarity of people on the issue. Favouring these results are western Europeans in which 7 out of 8 countries believes that it is the government responsibility to ensure a decent standard of living among its citizens with Italy being the highest, followed by Spain, and Netherlands (Simmons et. al, 2018). On the other hand, it is statement number 8 which got the lowest mean, implying the widespread belief the respondents have toward using territorial conquest to improve country's resources.

Conclusions

Diverse ideological beliefs are being possessed by each and between registered voters which was exhibited on their overlapping views on political concepts, social issues, and economic issues. Equally, the registered voters have mixed ideologies affirming the moderate level of ideological polarization. Hence, there is a healthy co-existence of multiple political views which indicates the effective working of democracy and a plural society that allows people to believe freely in what they want.

Moreover, the registered voters are moderately divided in their feeling towards their in- group and out-group. Both optimistic and pessimistic feelings and views are being expressed on an average level. However, instead of being hostile towards their counterpart, they appeared to be welcoming and understanding. Also, without elections in the corner, people can forget their differences as it is inevitable for them to interact with random people with different political beliefs daily. It appears that they do not let their political differences affect their feelings.

Lastly, ideologies and feelings are inevitably associated and relational which indicates that as the registered electorates become divided in their ideological beliefs the more that they will express hostility on different ideologies and its adherents, and affability on their own.

Recommendations

The government may institutionalize mechanisms and platforms such as open public discourse and public opinion from which the registered can express their ideological beliefs which would reflect their ideals and aspirations and can be used as foundation in the formulation of project, program, and policies. In that way, everyone will be afforded an opportunity to be heard that might increase the level of political participation among the voters and would reduce the hostility towards out-groups. Anti-discrimination ordinances may also be made on the basis of ideological differences to assure equal opportunities. Likewise, the Commission on Elections may devise a strategic plan on how strong affective polarization could be prevented during elections. They may adopt stronger election rules and regulations that will prohibit political parties and candidates in doing polarizing acts during campaigns. It is also advised to the

registered voters to be understanding and try to listen to one another to avoid fights and trouble. Lastly, further studies shall be conducted related to polarization to address the gap of this study and to obtain

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study the researchers followed the ethical considerations to uphold confidentiality, transparency, and trust between the researchers and the respondents. The researchers provided an Informed Consent Form (ICF) to the selected respondents. The ICF stressed that the participants' views and opinions would only be used for research purposes and would not be used to hurt, discriminate against, or objectify them in any manner. Everything that the participants say will not be made public and will be kept strictly between the researchers. All information provided will be treated with utmost confidentiality and respect. In doing the study, the researchers observed the Data Privacy Act of 2012 which (1) safeguards the privacy of people while the free flow of information is permitted to foster innovation and growth; (2) rules the gathering, recording, structuring, storage, improve or modification, restoration, consultation, usage compounding, blocking, deletion, or elimination of personal data; and (3) assures that the international data protection standards are being complied by the Philippines. The researchers intend to protect the respondents' anonymity by just using the survey questionnaire and quantified data for this study. The collected data will be deleted and will not be reproduced in any way once the study is concluded.

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